

Importance of Public Communication Campaigns and Art Activities in Social Education

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Abstract—Universities have an important role in social education in many aspects. In terms of creating awareness and convincing public about social issues, universities take a leading position for public. The best way to provide public support for social education is to develop public communication campaigns. The aim of this study is to present a public communication model which will be guided in social education practices. The study titled “Importance of public communication campaigns and art activities in Social Education” “is based on the following topics: Effects of public communication campaigns on social education, Public relations techniques for education, communication strategies, Steps of public relations campaigns in social education, making persuasive messages for public communication campaigns, developing artistic messages and organizing art activities in social education. In addition to these topics, media planning for social education, forming a team as campaign managers, dialogues with opinion leaders in education and preparing creative communication models for social education will be taken into consideration. This study also aims to criticize social education Case studies in Turkey. At the same time, some communicative methods and principles will be given in the light of communication campaigns within the context of this notice.

Keywords—Art activities in social education, Persuasive communication, Public communication campaigns, Public relations techniques for education

I. INTRODUCTION

THE dimension of informing society in public education, one of the most important communicational environments in institutions is the public relations campaigns. "Hence a sort of campaign management devoted to the education of society and communicational process management should be carried out. One of the most important responsibilities on this field is on the universities having science and art centers. Public relations campaigns, when applied particularly within the social responsibility constitute a strategical platform on informing the society. In this respect, university's constituting a field of initiative in public education, which becomes one with the name of the university itself and gaining respect among the society are possible with the communicational campaigns. For instance, university's undertaking the education on the subjects of "Making Peace with Other and Negotiating with Differences" and it's becoming one with this subject by organizing public relations campaigns that raise social responsibility awareness and its being cited as the solution-maker of the subject form a rather healthy structure on the basis of the educational politics of the university.

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The activities that contribute most to the communicational campaigns are the activities of art. University's evaluating the activities of art as an expression for creating a communication with society forms a strong perception on public opinion. At this juncture, presenting a campaign management model and fulfilling an accurate public relation activity management provide a strategical support particularly for the process of persuasion of the public opinion and on the constitution of a persuasive mode of communication.

II. QUALITY TOPIC SELECTION AND MESSAGE MANAGEMENT ON PUBLIC EDUCATIONAL CAMPAIGNS

Social campaigns have a big responsibility on the education of society. This responsibility simultaneously is a part of credit management strategies especially for the public institutions.

Among the studies on the education of public those four principles are the leading ones. "Using learners values and social interests to determine the purpose, direction and character of the learning process; making the social practice of the learners the basic content of the study process, linking the learners practice to the historical development of society, drawing on lessons and experiences of other progressive groups to improve learner practice" [1].

The management of public relations campaigns and communicational strategies for the benefit of the education of society should be detailed under strong titles. The first stage on the public relations campaigns devoted to the education is for the institution that manages the campaign to determine on a public educational strategy. Such effort was seen in 1890's in U.S.A. and the "Committee of Ten" which was established in 1892 and the "Committee of Seven" which was established in 1896 in U.S.A. carried out studies for the education of society [2].

One of the most significant stages of the public relations campaigns is for the company to have a strong idea. The universities are the institutions particularly to take the topic of developing and producing of an idea as a goal. That is why integrating with public opinion via strong ideas and meeting on a common point is a subject that elevates the success of the public relations campaign to it's utmost. The search conferences that would take place within the body of inter-university units are effective public relations activities to reveal that strong education oriented idea. In this regard, every and each unit should open the question "On which topics we should educate the society as our conscientious mission?" up for discussion and along with academic and administrative personnel students should also attend that discussion. On a search conference that takes place in the faculty itself an answer should be sought for this question and the

infrastructure of the idea should be well established. At the same time such kind of discussions will provide a quality topic selection. Because universities should determine on steady communication politics and should also put forward accurate fields of discussions.

In order to maintain the achievement of those aims stated above, the first step is to primarily specify the themes of education and to select the subject headings. On this subject, universities' starting this out with subjects regarding the future of country and country agenda and simultaneously arranging educational campaigns, in which the universities are perceived as the representatives of the problems of city or region they belong to, are realistic communicational politics.

On accurement of public education by means of Public relations campaigns, after the designation of subjects and themes as the first step, the aims of the campaigns should be luculently stated. The communicational representation of the goals of campaign and the manner of explanandum is one of the strongest headings of the message management dimension of the campaign and should aswell be approached with professional mode of communication. The campaign should be structured on the most persuasive mode. At this point university should act with persuasive communicational techniques. The campaign should be steadily positioned and the message of the campaign should be persuasive in the eye of the target groups.

In order for the campaign to take on a persuasive dimension and to be persuasive with it's messages" the campaign should arrange educational campaigns on topics "addressing to the public opinion and representing it's conscience."Durkheim put forward the concept of the duality of human nature. Mankind has two sorts of conscience one is "personal" the other is "societal". "On mechanic societies the "personal" and the "societal" consciences are the same. But on organic societies, personal and societal consciences are different, separate and in conflict "[3].One of the most important aims of social responsibility campaigns is to mobilize the conscience of public opinion and to support this conscience with steady strategies on communicational platforms by converting the personal conscience to societal conscience. University's mobilizing the public opinion and vocalizing it on certain topics, is simultaneously effective at utmost in presenting persuasive messages, but apart from that it maintains a prestigious perception and a respectable positioning on public opinion. Therefore, university, should open it's doors to the people and should carry out public oriented forums by arranging forum activities.

Throughout the process of forming a public opinion on any idea, the discussion of that idea should be put in field of discussion. Universities, with the developing democratic participation perspectives, are the most important public domains where the discussions are administered. The institutional studies on this subject are given the meaning via public domain theory."According to this theory people could discuss the topics they are interested in on certain mediums. The places for them to express such discussions and thoughts can be halls and cafes. According to Habernas, Public

institutions functioned crucially in terms of the formation of culture of democracy, though initially the minority of the population is in those discussions"[4]. All those public relations activities arranged under the leadership of university before campaign, provides the relevant idea to get in to circulation. The university's putting the public oriented surveys into practice about designated major headings and determining on a basic field of ignorance is an important step. One of the most important aims of public relations campaigns is to convert the fields of ignorance into knowledge and information. On the grounds that universities are the science production centers, the leading role is on the universities about the subject of arranging public relations campaigns with its informing dimension. Hence, universities to receiving the opinions of varying groups and institutions before the campaign and putting the message management into practice in accordance with those opinions, provides fields of views to act within the campaign before anything else. This field of view's being an objective field of view, and each idea's being equally approached, stabilizes the perception of the university as a reliable source and is one of the basic points of the mobilization of the campaign.

The campaign managers should primarily represent the reliability of the source of the institution arranging the campaign at the highest level possible, and the starting point should be provided through the fact of this reliable information. Aristotle defines the reliability of the source on persuasive communication as ethos. "According to Aristotle, persuasion succeeds or fails based on three basic types of artistic and inartistic proof. First persuasion depended on source's credibility or ethos much as it does today, which is why to testimonial is such an effective persuasive tactic" [5].

After the determination of themes and negotiation over headings, the other phase is the message management. In order for the messages to hold together and to be perceived as persuasive, university, as a very important part of the campaign management, should strengthen that message management. The first thing for the university to do within the frame of that message management is to set up a rather steady strategy on the subject of being a reliable addressee and a rapporteur on public opinion.

For instance, on a public relations campaign arranged by a university with the aim of maintaining societal common sense and placing the reconciliation culture university should be provided with it's own integration. The tolerance and negotiating with differences should become a part of that university's culture of institution and be supported with politics. University's hosting the activities symbolizing the negotiation with differences and placing this as a strong public relations activity politics is a consistent step. Besides, feeling a strong constitution struggling with every kind of discrimination within the university and this constitution's being supported with communicational politics increases the persuasiveness.

Therefore, It is necessary for the university to strengthen the perception of advocating the values that campaign possess at the outset, and to make it an important part of it. In this

particular, to extend the culture of reconciliation and to conduct the peace talks, all the communication techniques that are applied should be analyzed. "The ending of violence is often regarded as the principle objective in a peace process, or at least as an important first step towards settlement. In many process, including South Africa, Israel-Palestine and Northern Ireland, ceasefires were preceded by secret negotiations between the representatives of guerillas and either government or other intermediaries. [6].

University's launching a campaign named "signatures for 1000 Universities" within the frame of the negotiation of difference oriented educational campaign, can be evaluated as a part of this strong message management. University's preparing a social contract bearing the name of making peace with other and negotiating with differences, it's opening this contract for 1000 universities' academicians signature worldwide and launching a signature campaign via social media is a steady emphasis that the university implements on the persuasiveness of the campaign.

Similarly, university's carrying out joint senate meetings with other universities in the same country to establish a steady message management, and to strengthen the consistency of the message and to present messages as several universities' joint senate decisions on the subject of struggling with differences are the communicational politics strengthening the persuasiveness of the campaign in terms of message management. The most important mission on strengthening public education via communicational campaigns is the ability of communication molding a public opinion. And also in order to constitute a public opinion on the subject of public education, it is necessary for public relations and communicational campaigns to be managed with strategies that can affect the sharers. In this particular, a campaign management model should be set up to manage with negotiations via public education, having wide range of commitment, and the approach of communicational professionalism. The campaigns, at first stage, should constitute a wide range of commitment and a negotiation on the subject of public education.

Making an exact definition of social responsibility in terms of universities and other establishments as well as defining which social responsibility target will be aimed is a significant stage of this consensus. "A host of models, categories and taxonomies have been developed in an attempt to define CSR. Carroll(1979)described three elements that constitute a model of "corporate social performance ": a basic definition of CSR, the range of social areas for which corporations have responsibility and the range of corporate responses to social issues" [7]. Initial target within the frame of communication management is to create a public power for the campaign. A campaign to get the support and trust of the public is to leave a great impression in the society.

A. The Suggestion of Effective Campaign Scale on Public Education

One of the most significant points on conducting communicational campaigns on the subject of public

education is the determination of the points the society requires most as a necessity related to the education of the society and the arrangement of the campaigns aiming to enhance the public education on those subjects. The selection of the accurate topic titles would provide the campaign to be configured on an accurate communicational platform and would enhance the communicational power of the campaign. For the selection of the topic, a scale consisting of 22 *clause and preferential public education campaigns* under the name of

"The Necessity of Public Education". Those 22 clauses can be lined up as follows;

- 1.Selecting a topic dominating the future of the society and it's level of development
- 2.Being a subject contributing to societal reconciliation and peace
- 3.Being a subject intended for correcting the misinformation and basic delusions
- 4.The selection of the educational topics strengthening democracy
- 5.Selecting the topics regarding the community health care
- 6.The emphasis on campaigns regarding the citizenship and the social rights
- 7.The campaign themes interiorizing initiative on the fields of art and culture
- 8.The selection of the topics protecting the national culture and service
- 9.The selection of the educational titles aiming human rights and world peace
- 10.The selection of the campaign topics featuring mutualization and humanistic values
- 11.The arrangement of various communicational campaigns regarding the subject of environment
- 12.The selection of the topic titles with the theme of "Respect to differences"
- 13.The selection of the titles basing on creating an awareness and aiming to be informed about various subjects not yet spoken in the social agenda but the effects of which would be perceived in the future.
- 14.The selection of the topic titles incapsulating the higher education to be conducted under the leadership of the universities
- 15.The selection of the communicational campaign themes incapsulating technological progress and precession
- 16.The selection of the topic titles intended for scientific progress and research
- 18.The selection of the campaign titles improving the reading habits on society
- 19.The selection of the public education titles reinforcing the civil society
- 20.Social educational campaigns for handicapped
- 21.The educational campaigns intended for creating consciousness and sheltering the individuals suffering from violence and etc.in society
- 22.The social campaigns for struggling with natural disasters and cooperation

Those 22 basic topics, can be evaluated as subjects determining within the frame of the dimension of public education. The education campaigns arranged in this particular, is simultaneously a consciousness of social responsibility and conscientious sensitivity. On the determination of those topics professional communication studies should be held and various communication strategies should be developed.

The supreme point of acquisition on public education campaigns; is the augmentation of awareness. As Communication and public relations campaigns are the campaigns giving awareness contribute significantly to the public education. At this point when selecting a plot, every societies' specific dynamics, experiences, cultures and traditions, the social fabric and etc. play a significant role. On the selection of topic another determining process is for the campaign to detect a gap and to be aiming to resolve that gap. For instance, the focusing point to be researched, on a campaign aiming to increase reading habits in a country is the detection of the deficiency for the reading habits. At this point a field of gap should be determined on. The meaning of gap is the detection of the title which is slubbered and unnoticed yet has an effect on topic. The accurate selection of the topic on a campaign simultaneously provides the campaign to occur on a suitable communicational platform as well. Hence another noteworthy phase on the selection of the topic is the expectations and the necessities of the society. At this point it is necessary to read the expectations of the society accurately and to fulfill those expectations accurately. Therefore, before putting the public education campaigns into practice, the social studies pertaining to those studies should be elaboratively structured. The expectations of the society regarding to that topic, and necessities should be detected and the campaign should be managed aiming to resolve those expectations and necessities. Besides the issue management on public communicational campaigns should be directed, offering new opportunities to the target group and presenting resolution oriented facilitative methods[8].The campaign, in its own right, should demonstrate the practical vital solution offers on various issues that the society suffers from.

A campaign's identifying itself with the coordinating institution and arousing a respect towards that institution is the one of the most prestigious acquisition that the campaign gains. Therefore, a point of creating an initiative identifying with the campaign itself is rather important. The campaigns' creating of values identifying with itself at the outset is the constituent of the campaign strategy. To illustrate, when a public educational campaign is organized on the subject of "Living with differences and Understanding the other", the campaign should establish values belonging to itself and remembered with itself and to be respected.

For instance, Within the frame of a campaign commenced with the leadership of Mardin Artuklu University, which is at the forefront with it's studies regarding to this subject, in Turkey, In the total of world's most prestigious 500 universities, substantiating a senate meeting on the same moment, in the same hour and signing on a common decision

text gives a respectable value to the campaign. Theming the census of living with differences around the world is emphasizing the campaign globally as well as paving the way for 500 universities to undertake the education on this subject with their common decision and enterprises. This study would be called as the Mardin Artuklu University initiative on international literature and would enable the university to earn a respectable and reputable structure.

As it is defined in the illustration of Mardin Artuklu University, the mission that the campaign possesses and it's dimension of value is a deterministic philosophy. Within the frame of determination of the main titles of a topic about an educational campaign on "Recognition of Violence and Female Victims of Domestic Violence" is a necessity of an effective campaign management. In order to struggle with violence, recognizing the violence at the outset, determining it's reasons and the ways to struggle with it, carrying out studies on this topic to increase the societal sensitivity and providing a consubstantiation by introducing victims of violence are the main headings of the educational openings. Educating the society for the struggle against violence, is the best example for the management of communicational campaigns and educational studies. The undertaking of those educational studies by 10 to 12 civil society organizations and their managing a joint communicational campaigns is also important in the sense of bringing the power of the civil society and it's efficiency on campaigns to the forefront. In this context, In all the primary-secondary educational institutions and in universities in Turkey, the reading of the messages and calls which are written by the victims with their own pencils in the same hour, and simultaneously providing this call to be published on the full front page of the newspapers are the crucial communicational efforts effecting the success of societal education on this topic.

On a call to be shared under the name of "A letter to the Society from the Victims of Violence" using a few pages of letter each of which includes a few lines of testification from the women personally suffering greatly from violence and demands from the society to struggle against violence and the evaluation of this letter as it were a manifest on the struggle against violence provide an accurate communicational route to the society. Therefore, communicational campaigns are the strong supporting points on communication with society in terms of adding a value and a symbol to the societal struggle.

B. Public Education, Social Sensitivity and the Public Opinion

Societal education is a process of education simultaneously pioneering the society and increasing the consciousness and the sensitivity of the society. Broadening the perception of sensitivity on certain fields in the society and constituting a sensitive society are the main goals of societal education. The communicational campaigns are fairly the flags of this sensitivity. Those are the campaigns which stabilize the societal sensitivity and constitute fields of sensitivity.

In order to constitute a sensitive society, it is necessary to attract the attention of society to both the campaign and the

theme of campaign and to provide the discussion of the topic at the outset.

Within the frame of a topic and an idea, it is rather important to create a public opinion and is a strong negotiation on the point of societal values and aims. "Public opinion as social control is centered on insuring a sufficient level of consensus within society on the community's values and goals"[9]. For the constitution of public opinion; it is primarily necessary to provide the talking and discussion of this topic on communicational platform. It is also necessary to provide the society to face with that matter and to make sense of that matter accurately. In this sense constituting a sensitive society is one of the significant tasks of public relations and communicational campaigns. In order to reveal that sensitivity it is necessary to transmit the sensitive messages within the frame of commitment as wide as possible to majority of the society and the target group via accurate communicational mediums. Constituting sensitive campaign messages are one of the most preferential goals of the communicational campaigns aiming the societal education. To exemplify, when acted from the point of arrangement of an educational campaign with the joint acts of Dolmabahçe Palace and Topkapı Palace in Turkey to preserve the cultural heritage it is necessary to create a virtually iconized sensitive message and to increase the interest to that educational campaign. On this subject with the leadership of UNESCO president in Dolmabahçe Palace arranging a workshop in which the representatives and supervisors of the important palaces and museums around the world attend and signing on an international contract on the subject of preserving the cultural heritage of world and education of society is an accurate effort of communication on the subject of giving a sensitive message. On the point of constituting a sensitive message, using the symbols and common points is an element that increases the communicational strength of the campaign. One of the greatest advantages of conducting the societal education via communicational campaigns is that the campaign to increase the sensitivity. This sensitive point of view gives acceleration to the campaign. *Hence those points below are suggested on constituting a sensitive message;*

- 1.The topic on which the sensitivity demanded to be constituted should be well explained
- 2.Individual and societal initiatives are to be accentuated on
- 3.The identification with subject is to be provided
- 4.Personal attendance to the campaign should be provided
- 5.If there are sufferings and pains experienced regarding to that topic those should be conveyed to the society
- 6.The negative effects of topic about the future should be clearly emphasized
- 7.The accurate information providing the sensitivity should be given in the right time
- 8.Persuasive messages should be prepared and process of persuasiveness of the campaign should be well managed
- 9.The importance and the necessity of mobilization should be emphasized.
- 10.The materials of education should be transferred to the target group within the process.

III. MESSAGE MANAGEMENT ON PUBLIC EDUCATION AND PERSUASIVE COMMUNICATION

The perception of messages that are presented in campaigns as persuasive messages is quite important particularly on the field of public education. At this point in the communicational campaigns about public education the particulars that the messages should possess from the point of persuasive communication can be lined up as follows: Primarily the message should come up with a plausible and an acceptable claim and goal. the message should be perceived as a plausible message by the target group. For instance, on a public educational campaign started for developing the quality standards in higher education in a university in Turkey such emphasis as "The Leader University in the 100th year of the Republic,2023" can not be rated as plausible can be perceived as propaganda intentional. But the target of "Being in one of the first 100 or 500 University" is a plausible that can be accepted by the target group. One starting point to be paid attention in campaign messages is to structure the message out of the range of propaganda themes. Another important point on public educational communicational campaigns is that the message should be convenient with communicational medium that it is in and should possess the persuasive characteristic. For instance, the biggest indicator of that success on social media is that how much the message is shared and repeated by countless people on communicational accounts such as Facebook, Twitter. Therefore, for instance on a public educational campaign initiated with an aim to prevent the fanaticism in football, The selected famous artists and footballers' presenting the campaign messages on their personal social media accounts and their sharing those messages on an increasing rate is an accurate example for the persuasiveness and the positioning of the message correspondingly on social media environment.

The most convenient positioning of the message most accordingly to the communicational medium where it is presented and it's sharing with the target group increases the persuasiveness of the message. The ones who would represent that message on newspapers are the columnists. Hence the campaign management should detail the media plan which encapsulates the elements with a rather detailed way such as the specific features of every communicational medium, target group, readability, rating, follow ability, prestige and etc.

In order to present persuasive messages on public educational campaigns, a reliable course of action and a solution should be presented. At the same time, a method of negotiation should be developed. On this subject a 6 step of communicational plan is advised.

Listen, understand the other's point of view, show a concern for the relationship, look for common ground, invent new problem-solving options, reach an agreement based on what's fair[10].A reliable course of action elevates the reputation of the campaign. On a campaign carried out by a woman association on Athens to attract the attention to the common problems of woman living in Europe and to raise awareness among the society, the associations presenting a study and a report with the name of " The common working

report of 1000 Female scientists devoted to the betterment of woman labors working conditions – The initiative of Athens” is a reliable mission in terms of bringing a solution route. On the communicational campaigns devoted to societal education, The preparation of the messages via a joint study and a joint spirit of campaign with partners in other words with target groups elevates the persuasiveness of those messages. At this point, in order to constitute a persuasive perception an accurate identification is required about what the target group demands. “An individual’s state of mind is a very important thing to consider in the persuasion process. It is also very important to know the other’s person’s desired state of mind. When you determine this, you can persuade the person by showing him how to get there”[11]. For instance, when a university in France organizes a communicational campaign to attract the attention to the societal responsibility about the handicapped, the selection of the slogan by handicapped personally and its sharing with public opinion on forums arranged jointly with handicapped would provide the trust and support of the sharers. The acceptability rate of the message prepared with the statements such as “The University of Paris is embracing the self messages of the handicapped and is sharing with the people of Paris” would encapsulate a broader space in the universe of communication.

On a public educational campaign arranged by the Ministry of Education in Turkey aiming to behave the tourist with the most righteous way of communication, Ministry’s sharing the campaign messages by getting in touch with tourists that visit Turkey on certain periods and receiving their ideas and suggestions provides a model about the resolution. For instance conveying such messages as “Spanish tourists demand cultural guidance from we Turks!” or “Greek tourists demand a better accommodation from we Turks” or “German tourists demand a distant sincerity” by the tourist in propria persona is a persuasive communicational study carried out with sharers jointly. Thus propulsion of target group analysis with detailed manner and actively making the sharers a part of campaign by the campaign management are the significant steps. On the stage of pre-campaign and constituting a message various public relations activities structuring the healthy communication with sharers should be planned and this should also be evaluated as an important part of activity management.

On the communicational campaigns aiming the societal education one of the strategic elements of the constitution of a persuasive message is a frame of loyalty towards the campaign. Institutional expresses many values about the institution. “When I think of the words loyal or loyalty, I also think of words such as dedication, fidelity, reliability, dependability, constancy and steadfastness. I also think of the word loyalty when I think about how people are loyal to particular cause, faiths, sports team, family member or spouse [12].

Holding a public opinion, loyal to the values and targets that it presents, creates one of the most respectable frames in campaign activity. One of the most significant requirements of constituting that loyalty is for the campaign to carry the values

respected by entire community at the outset. Those values should be expressed to the community via all the communicational efforts and techniques rather transparently. For instance, The starting points such as “The betterment of working conditions in society” , “Making a claim to the professional ethical values”, “Preventing the child abuse in work life” , “making a claim to the cultural and spiritual values”, “Consociating on a problem that handicapped suffers from” should be expressed with respectable values. In the context of goal that campaign aims, the organizing institution should assure the society on the subjects of possessing higher ideals for campaign and It’s self devotion without looking out for it’s own interest. Being a reliable and a neutral flag of a struggle is a deterministic communicational element on providing the loyalty and enabling the sharers to feel the ideals jointly in their hearts.

Another element solidifying the persuasiveness of the message on communicational campaigns about public education is the emphasis of “a shared better future”. Public educational studies aim a sharing including common targets for a stronger future.

IV. REPUTATION STRATEGIES AND CAMPAIGN MANAGEMENT

One of the most affirmative acquisitions on the communicational campaigns carried out by universities and other institutions is for the campaign to add a respect to it. “Reputation is described by The Penguin English Dictionary as 1: overall quality or character as seen or judged by others; 2: fame, celebrity, 3: recognition by other people of some characteristic or ability” [13]. Being respectable means having a credibility on public opinion and emerging as an effectual power. When evaluated from the perspective of reputation management the effect of public educational campaigns in terms reputation management on universities for instance is felt in public opinion in the context of being perceived as an effectual power.

Public educational campaigns enable the universities to be perceived as an effectual power. Directing and leading the society via public educational campaigns gives the university “an effective communicational power”. The biggest elements of the communicational power are to be able to mobilize the public opinion and to be a representative of that movement. Public educational campaigns, on that point, are the campaigns mobilizing and determining the communicational strength and are also the significant parts of reputation strategies.

To exemplify; A university’s leading a campaign in France in the name of “The education about the Democracy Culture for the Middle Eastern Countries’ societies via social media” indicates to a campaign management developing the reputation of the university and increasing the credibility on public opinion. Universities, particularly on such topics, should concentrate on public educational campaigns. Universities’ bringing internet sites into service for each of Middle Eastern Countries and their calling for them on social media environments, Opening discussion forums about democracy, sharing documents of democracy, the expressions

of democratic openings, the importance of democracy and an emphasis of democratic society on those sites opened with the leadership of the university for each of those countries, is a revoltingly beneficial work of societal education and an emphasis for the development of international reputation of the university. In such a campaign the most important phase is the proper planning of that educational campaign by developing the reputation.

University should constitute a squad of esteem. Institutional respect is a complicated process encapsulating leadership, vision, reliability, social and environmental responsibility along with knowledge and ability. On this squad personally presided at, by the university rector, social media experts should assuredly participate. For the reason that campaign to be carried out via social media, the leading social media experts within the university and country should participate in that squad. Moreover on that subject, the social media experts from Middle Eastern countries should be contacted and in order for the public educational campaign to be successful, those leading figures should personally be invited to the meetings which are held in universities and be accepted as the rapporteurs of the campaign.

The second phase on the democracy education campaign that would be carried out by university are the experts play a role as the leading figures on the subject of democracy, and to plan the content of the democracy education. On this topic, in addition to the faculty members in the university who are able to instruct democracy lectures out of the relevant units, a support should be obtained from the NGO'S nongovernmental organizations in France and the selected civil society leaders should be brought in the leaders of that education. Therefore, to arrange the main titles of the democracy education that would be carried out by university, the basic topics of this education should be designated at the university with the democracy focused nongovernmental organizations in France, and a debate should be developed on how to be able to lecture the middle eastern societies about democracy and how to be able to position the social media leg of that. The invitation of nongovernmental organizations to the university without any discrimination and the organization of meetings with frequent intervals would provide the support of civil initiative.

At this point, the thing that is necessary to do is to reach the sharers via social media on democracy education. The analysis of target group should be well structured. In this context strategies should be developed upon the target groups. The civil organisms in middle east, universities, the middle eastern youth using social media, authors, artists and middle eastern media are the first sharers to come into mind in this respect. The campaign management strategies on how to be able to carry out the education of democracy via social media with those sharers should be structured with a strong content.

Within the frame of the campaign for instance, a separate working group should be constituted for each middle eastern countries. Then the universities that would be contacted for each country should be selected. For example, within the frame of universities that are selected from Egypt, it is necessary to reach approximately 200.000 Egyptian university

students and to make a sharing on the subject of democracy with each of them. At this point, invitation by the leading French university to the other universities in France to the campaign and hence stabilizing the national dimension of the campaign enables the internal public opinion to focus on target and positions the campaign management on solid grounds.

In this context, The selection of volunteer university students, can be evaluated as an effective communicational steps. In order to reach and enable peer to peer communication for 200.000 university students in Egypt via social media, 200.000 University students in Paris are incorporated into the campaign voluntarily and each of them are charged to get in touch with Egyptian university students within the frame of the campaign management. Making a peer to peer contact is an element to increase the awareness, it's spreading on a large area, recognizability and reputation. Similarly the non governmental organizations in France are expected to get in touch with non governmental representatives in Middle East and to structure the education of democracy. In this regard it is necessary to get in touch with universities in Middle East and to position those universities as the leading figures of societal campaign education. In order to provide such campaign to be successful it is necessary to receive the supports of the initiators of public opinion in Middle Eastern companies and to make them the symbols of campaign. Hence it is necessary to invite journalists, authors, artists, students representatives and University rectors to the campaign in France by the university itself organizing the campaign along with maintaining the supports of those people.

In such public educational campaign, via which means of social media is democracy to be introduced and the content of communication are rather significant. In order to convey the topic titles such as the definition of democracy, it's important tools, the fundamental features of a democratic society media and democracy, civil society and democracy and etc... to the Middle Eastern society via social media various educational materials and messages should be prepared and shared.

The strength of molding public opinion and effecting the masses is simultaneously a strength executing the responsibility of university's being a societal pioneer. Herewith societal educational studies, establish messages and themes of reputation for universities and other institutions. Another important point in terms evaluating the societal educational campaigns within the frame of reputation management strategies is to pioneer the societal renovations and openings and simultaneously to indicate a societal opening for the educational campaign which is performed.

In order for the educational campaigns to be evaluated as the campaigns effecting the reputation of the institutions, the content of the campaign should be levelly prepared at the same time. Thus, for campaign management to generate serious communicational planning on the subjects of which messages to be added to the campaign and for messages to be shared on the right points within the body of the campaign the campaign management should make a point of message management. In order for the messages which, would be presented to the target group, to be persuasive the messages

should carry strong arguments. "The message remains a centerpiece of persuasion-a complex, fascinating one, to be sure. It revolves around arguments, but arguments are diverse entities. They can be logical, statistical, anecdotal or highly emotional" [14].

The point of messages to be the oral and written expression symbols of a struggle, an opening and an initiative is the point of mobilization. Simultaneously the campaign should possess a strong content carrying stable and strength messages, which are calling out to consciences, participation and co-operation oriented and leaving a mark on the hearts of the target group.

The right selection of the symbols representing the campaign on public educational campaigns is necessary. For instance in an educational campaign with the theme of Freedom of Press in Middle East, the selection of the foreign journalists who were murdered in Syria as the symbol of the campaign adds a consistency and a reputation to the campaign. In a campaign arranged by international Press Institute with the cooperation among universities, the American journalist Marie Colvin and French photo journalist Remi Ochlik who lost their lives in a hotel on a rocket assault where they accommodated in Bab Amr district of Humus can be evaluated as the symbols of campaign. Those two journalists each of whom are the pioneers of their own professions are but two names that would find the support of the public opinion and would also address to the hearts of society as the heroes of society in an educational campaign with the theme of Freedom of Press in Middle East. The black band used by journalist Colvin who lost one of her eye while she was pursuing news in a fire in Sri Lanka can be used as the symbol of the campaign. Besides this symbol would also be rather inspiring for the campaign to be persuasive in the minds of the target group and to be turned into the awareness via societal consciousness. The campaign symbols should constitute a strong correlation between the values of campaign and should express that relation with utmost reputation in the minds of target group. Those strong symbols simultaneously make the campaign message possible to be shared by hundred of thousands and even millions via means molding public opinion.

For instance today one of the most -public opinion constituting- channel is the communicational channel. In an educational campaign aiming the freedom of press stated above black band's being shared on every social networking sites and even it's being the flag of joint conscience and commitment renders the respect and the support of the public opinion.

V. CAMPAIGN'S CREATION OF ITS OWN MODE OF COMMUNICATION

On public educational campaigns, the campaigns creation of it's own mode of communication are one of the factors determining the efficiency of the mode of communication. In this point the healthiest communicational method is for each target group to develop a mode of communication compatibly to those priorities by analyzing their own features."Some publics are intimately connected with an organization, for example it's employees.

Others have a more remote connection, for example those making occasional visit to the web site. Some publics will have an amicable relationships with the organization, others will find themselves in opposition to it. Again, the public relations practitioner needs to have a clear perception of these relationships and to gauge their changing nature"[15]. One of the strongest communicational steps is for the campaign to constitute it's own channel of communication. The broadcasting of a radio named "Voice of Democracy" in the subject of education of democracy in Middle East via social media and this radio's being the symbol of the campaign and this radios having it's own communicational channel is simultaneously the constitution of a mode of communication of this campaign. In this regard the institutions should structure their campaign activities in the frame of mode of communication they aim. On the point of coming up with it's own mode of communication for the campaign, "Communicational Activity Model on the Public Education Intentional Communicational Campaigns" is advised. One of the starting points of this model is the constitution of communicational universe within which the campaign acts. The universe of the campaign should be drawn in a frame as wide as possible. "Strategical communication means to develop the strategical positioning of the institutions as integrated with their general strategies" [16]. Another phase at this point is for the campaign to constitute their own specific volunteers. The voluntariness in campaign management is based on four basic principals. "Volunteerism implies active involvement, Volunteerism is uncoerced, Volunteerism is not motivated primarily by financial gain, Volunteerism focuses on the common good" [17]. One of the most important constitutions determining the success and the efficiency of the campaign are the voluntary organisms. Hence, campaigns constitution of a volunteer profile identifying with itself and the acceptance of that profile in the society as respectable would increase the interest towards the campaign. Campaigns convoking for voluntariness within the frame of campaign to recruit new volunteers and to define voluntariness persuasively is one of the steps recommended for the relevant subject. On this subject, the communicational channels, where the messages could be delivered as wide as possible, are the internet sites of the universities. Ege university's procurement of publishing the voluntariness call and the campaign as an announcement is on 1000 internet sites around the world as the result of established connections and exchanging letters is an effective step in the direction of evolvement of the campaign universe. Participating the announcement of the campaign on 1000 universities' internet sites enables the campaign to be discussed in a wide geography and carry the map of campaign to the international borders. Performing the efforts devoted to the handicapped as a communicational campaign would simultaneously constitute the initiative of voluntariness of campaign as well. A similar campaign approach in this particular is the procurement of the support of international media and the announcement of the campaign on the internet sites of certain countries' newspapers. Providing the participation of the voluntariness call on the internet sites

of respected newspapers by contacting the editors of those leading newspapers which have a strong power to create a public opinion strengthens the constitution of international public opinion within the frame of campaign.

Hence, as exemplified in the instance of Ege University, substantiation of an action such as everybody's shutting their eyes for two minutes on where they are in the same hour and at the same moment to appeal the attention to the problems of handicapped is a step devoted to the discussion of the problems of the handicapped in front of the public opinion. Activities of such kind would enable the campaign to create a mode of communication of its own. Within this scope, the organization of democratic campaigns and solution driven protest campaigns and pioneering the protest campaigns are among the activities constituting a respectable style. Campaign's being demonstrated as the symbol of the protest devoted to understanding each other within the frame of indulgence and dialogue would be evaluated as a respectable protest communicational activity on gaining its own style. Because protest demonstrations substantially create an impression of fights, conflicts and even violence. A protest demonstration performed within negotiation, understanding and dialogue can be efficient on the perception of the campaign as a societal symbol. One of the most important criteriums of the campaigns constituting a mode of communication specific to itself is for the people to recognize the campaign messages and to carry those messages in their daily lives.

Therefore, the campaign should set up the messages which could express the campaign itself to the society and the structures that could be identified in the minds of public. One of the most important aims of societal educational campaigns is the scaling the awareness of the society up to the designated level as the result of campaign. So, in the frame of the campaign it is necessary to provide the face to face communication of campaign rapporteurs with society. Today universities being in the first place, various societal educational campaigns organized by other institutions stay mostly within their own borders and they are clearly understood not to be the campaigns about which the society talk and discuss. Hence, the reason why the public educational campaigns are shaped with communicational campaigns is that those campaigns are also evaluated to be the campaign that the society talk and discuss about.

In order for the societal educational campaigns to have a mode of communication devoted to the society, the communicational techniques and strategies should be structured. On today's digital age, The communicational techniques that would be developed while communicating with the target group is situated in a much wider spectrum. "The digital age has also introduced emerging media or new media –additional layers of public relations campaign possibilities that include guerilla marketing, also known as PR stunts or viral marketing, and Internet marketing using chat rooms, blogs, UGC(user-generated content)sits and RSS(Really simple Syndication or Rich Site Summary)to attempt to initiate viral marketing"[18].

One of the starting points within the frame of that aim, is the planning of a joint action and a movement with the participation. For instance, on a public educational campaign to prevent traffic accidents, the acceptance of a white flag as a symbol, and the use of that flag on a specific day by all intracity and intercity public transport vehicles is an example of a reflection of the campaign in daily life. In order for the campaigns to be evaluated as the campaigns devoted to the society, the society should express a sensitivity in daily life. The utilization of the symbols that are mentioned before is also an efficient method. In order to enable the campaign to leave more impression as for devoted to the society, making the names, celebrated by the society, to be the faces of the campaign and ensuring the participation of the society is an efficient campaign activity.

The names, on whom the society indisputably negotiate, and whose prospects are in demand, and whose philosophy of life arouse respect, should be selected as the faces of the campaign. Therefore, on the selection of an individual who represents a campaign best; the elements such as the biography of that person, the history of his/her career, his/her reputation, his/her campaign aims, his/her reputation among society, his/her philosophy of life should be evaluated and the accurate role model should be selected that presents a campaign to the society at the end of those evaluations.

The substation of the campaigns devoted to the campaign, provides the constitution of the universe of the campaign at the widest scale. Hence, In order to receive a support particularly from non governmental organizations and to enable the scales of campaign to be felt among the society, the mobilization of the civil initiative should be provided.

Especially in universities, the ideal procuration of the integration between university and society is an important dimension for the universities to open its gates to public. The recognition of university by public, its being cognizant of its projects, internalizing its aims, are the important steps of the integration between university and community.

From the viewpoint of societal educational campaigns, the integration between university and society matters greatly. The universities providing the university and society integration can obtain a better success on public education. Therefore, universities and other institutions should express themselves primarily in the cities and regions they are located in. In a city where a university is located, a public relations campaign started by a university aiming to develop the scientific researches and inventions can be evaluated within the frame of that scale.

Providing the university and society integration on such campaign is one of the preferential aims. It is required to enable the society to be a part of a campaign and to feel belonged to the campaign. University's establishing an exhibition within the borders of the campaign to make the society express their own inventions and interesting ideas and introducing the inventions of the public, and the positioning of that exhibition on certain locations outside the campus is simultaneously an example indicating to the pioneering of the

university for the society as well as protecting the ideas, inventions and suggestions of society.

The university's determining the best 20 inventions in the city and providing the introduction of those within the entire country and designating those as the starting point of the campaign are steps effecting the integration of the university and society affirmatively.

University's embracing the city culture in which it's located and organizing activities on that subject forms the healthy connections of communications between university and society. For instance within the frame of a campaign devoted to the preservation of a cultural heritage, university's establishing a public museums within the borders of the campus and demanding the exhibition of a ware, from each family in that city, which is thought to be representing that city best, is a situation strengthening the connections of the university with the city as well as the efficiency of the campaign.

Particularly on public educational campaigns organized with various creative public relations activities, it is necessary to provide the integration between the university and public. Such efforts, would constitute a perception such as the university is pioneering the city and paving the way for it and would pioneer the university to create a mode of communication of it's own.

A. Persuasive Codifications on Public Educational Campaigns

It is necessary for the campaigns, devoted to the public education, to display sensitivity on constituting persuasive messages while addressing to both the heart and the sense of the target group. The persuasive messages provide the campaign to stay within a more reliable platform. Introduction of persuasive messages has various methods. One of them is departing from the life stories that are experienced and coding the communicational messages with the inspirations granted by those life stories. Code, can be identified as any group of symbols which can be done in a such a way that seems meaningful to the people. "Everything, which has a group of component and a group of operations to emerge those components meaningfully, is called code. If we seek to understand anything whether to be a code or not, we should first isolate it's components, then we should check whether systematical ways could be found, to emerge those components we isolated "[19]. For instance, on a campaign aiming to create a public opinion on the importance of struggling with all kinds of discrimination in society, one of the most ideal methods on the presentation of persuasive methods is the participation of the messages which belong to the names devoted their lives on that in public opinion. A life story dedicated to a case particularly affects the success of the societal educational campaigns.

At this point, the evaluation of the names from the society, who became heroes in their own struggles, as a part of the campaign (not only the well-known names) strengthens the persuasiveness of the messages. For example on a communicational campaign initiated to increase the rate of

literacy in the countryside, the participation of the names in the campaign messages who completed his/her university education and can be a role model on that subject, is an accurate step. As the experienced success stories could constitute a heuristic perception is a route of communication for successful communicational campaigns. In order to be persuasive in public educational campaigns, the campaign should clearly emphasize the palpable effect and the change which is brought to the lives of people by campaign. The target group should believe that the campaign would constitute an affirmative "alteration" on them and public educational campaigns should convey that alteration persuasively. As a matter of fact the most predominant point of the campaign should be focused on that "alteration" theme.

The idea that joining the campaign brings a better life for people should be strongly transferred in campaigns in a communicational sense. For instance an educational campaign started by all universities for search and rescue operations in natural disasters focuses on saving people struggling for their lives and presenting their lives to them. A communicational theme shaped by university students and personnel as "You will gain brand new responsibility in your life by joining that search and rescue training. That talent will change your outlook on your life, and will provide you with a perspective towards life from an another window by making you strong individuals internalizing human values, making the campaign's effect on target group more meaningful.

Almost all of the public educational campaigns focus the person to on an alteration by means of education. The important thing is to code that alteration on such a style that enables the target group to understand with an accurate communicational language because alteration simultaneously carries resistance with it. "Thus, a major source of resistance to affective changes concerns the extent to which such change would require some change in, or reshuffling of, the relevant values. Attitudes based on important values would normally be expected to be more resistant to change than attitudes based on trivial values [20]. An accurate communicational language and a comprehensible campaign message defining the alteration decently, persuade the target group particularly to the necessity of campaign what is more, persuade the target group on the subject of joining the campaign and also provide the support of the campaign as clearly as it could convey that alteration.

It is necessary to emphasize that alteration in public educational campaigns mostly as an alteration devoted to future and constructing the future. An reasonable proportion of campaigns are using the slogan of "A better future" and start out from this point. The method of " A better future" and "building the future" themes and the most persuasive transferring for the campaign about the alteration on future are communicational campaigns. The theme of future should be divergently emphasized.

For instance, an educational campaign can be organized by a university or non-governmental organization for children devoted to the right use of social media. The usage of social media by children and the youth is a point directly effecting

their lives. At this point, the interest of children to social media is canalized on a false direction and their personality development is effected negatively. Particularly various internet games incentivize the children to wars and violence and are intensively played by children along with effecting the personality development of the children. On a public educational campaign which would educate the families and children and canalize them in to the right direction, it is necessary to start out from the point that those games abetting those children to crime by featuring the relation between child and crime. A communicational campaign that could be conducted with a message of "Let not our children to be the criminals of the future. Let's take the initiative for the future as the parents of those children" would give a bigger interest to the campaign as well as adding a better attendance.

It is also important to plan the right timing to meet the target group on the point of constituting messages via public educational campaigns and transferring of those messages by means of accurate communicational codes. The encoding of communicational messages by the campaign on the right time and campaigns tipping the scales of the element of time to it's favor is a situation serving the communicational purposes. This is such a situation to emphasize the idea of "it's time to make a move". It is necessary to share the theme "The right time to make a move" clearly with the target group. Therefore, the starting time of the campaign should be quite accurately determined. To illustrate, organizing an important sports competition for an educational campaign conducted for the donship, is a right timing to make a move. The violence and fanaticism in sports is situation effecting the youth and masses negatively. A communicational campaign conducted with the leadership of a university in France can be bestowed as an example to emphasize on the spirit of donship in sports and to struggle with that violence. Finally, the disaster in a sports competition in Egypt between the teams Al Masri and Al Ahri is still in minds. Therefore, university's doing a friendly match with the Ayn Shams, 2nd. Biggest university of Egypt, reprobating the violence in sports would catch an accurate starting point on this subject. In the frame of the campaign arranged with the slogan "It's high time to beat the violence in sports", the friendly match between two universities and the development of this concept with similar activities on varying branches of sports is an important step. The accurate message's being brought together with the target group on right timing within the societal educational campaigns, would provide the campaign management to be positioned on strong groundworks. The campaign management should set a course for communicational principals and techniques while providing the campaign to be truly perceived by target group via accurate activities an messages. Communicational campaigns present communicational practices on the accurate interpretation of the campaigns and the acceptability of the campaigns.

Another phase, from the viewpoint of messages, for the public educational campaigns to integrate with the target group is for the message to indicate to a questioning and self criticism, self evaluation and renovation. The public

educational campaigns indicate to the accurate route and enables individuals to question where they are. It is necessary for the campaign to use such themes and to provide the target group to question on their own minds. In other saying, it is necessary for the campaigns to posses the interrogating messages within. In this regard the codes of communication should be used accurately.

Interrogative messages are simultaneously the messages enhancing the persuasiveness of the campaign and devoted to mobilize the society. The messages devoted to mobilizing and promoting the attendance constitute the most striking headings of the societal educational campaigns. At this point, the main slogan of the campaign makes the strongest effect felt. For instance on a public educational campaign conducted synchronously by a university from each countries to develop the relations between Turkey and France, a campaign emphasis should be done to provide the attendance to the campaign. To exemplify, two university's constituting a non governmental organism under the name of "The Friendship by heart between Turkey and France" and it's demanding "virtual signatures" by the volunteers for that organism is a situation effecting the dimension of attendance for the communicational campaign. At the first stage voluntary organism's aiming 100.000 signatures and reaching this number is a proof that campaign presents persuasive messages in terms of attendance the campaign. For the campaign to use a slogan "A million Signature For Fellowship" includes an effort devoted to the mobilization. It is expected from the public educational campaigns to include a perceivable change of attitude or a reaction by the target group. With the influence of the campaign as in the following examples of being a member of a non governmental organization, donating, attending a marching, forming a work of art, reading a book, subscribing to a magazine, travelling abroad, or giving up smoking cigarettes, in short changing habits are the concrete dimensions of the campaign. Campaign should draw that palpable picture in the communicational perspective.

Therefore it is necessary to evaluate the targets that are reached during the campaign step by step and is also necessary to make some renovations and self-evaluations within the frame of the campaign. It is also necessary to share the success of the campaign with the target group and to invite and call the target group to the next phase of the campaign. For instance, A message such as "We reached 100.000 signatures on the campaign devoted to the Fellowship Of Turkey and France. And now we invite you to make a move to reach 500.000 signatures and to devise a personal project for the fellowship of Turkey and France is an example for that call.

VI. THE BASIC PRINCIPALS TO SET A MODEL ON PUBLIC EDUCATIONAL CAMPAIGNS

One of the most important stages in communicational campaigns aiming societal education is for such campaigns to set a model. For the campaigns to be prepared by starting from a model, draws a map which includes the contributions of the campaign devoted to future. Setting a campaign model on certain topics simultaneously constitutes a road map for other

campaigns as well as undertaking a social mission. The first stage of the campaign model is to organize a campaign administration team. The campaign administration should consist of strong characters who would lead forth the campaign. The leadership of the campaign should be comprehended on two stages. The former is, the organization administrators managing the organizational dimension of the campaign, the other is, the leaders and the heroes/heroines that the campaign created itself. The campaign model should study these two stages on the subject of campaign management.

The organizational administrators of the campaign, are the leaders preparing the plan of communicational flow of the campaign, managing the campaign and providing the movement of the campaign. The organizational administrators are suggested under three headings such as; strategist administrator, operational administrator, and the message management. Strategist administrators are the administrators who add ideas to the campaign, manage the dimension of idea of the campaign, and managing new activities and communicational strategies by conducting communicational strategies within an understanding of strategic thinking. The strategist campaign managers are at the same time the managers adding new values to the campaign. For instance, when a university decides to organize an educational campaign on international values of negotiation, they are the team members who would draw the notional frame of the campaign. That team of strategists does the researches on the subjects of which international values represent the negotiation and which international leaders are the pioneers of that negotiation and as a result of these researches that team determines the name and topic titles of the campaign, the main aims and the values dominating the campaign. Strategist administrators can evaluate the new values and strategies within and can suggest new activities as the campaign progresses and it enhances its integration with the target group. The team that would manage the message management is such a team constituting strong messages as well as structuring the communicational messages that the campaign seek to share with the target group in accordance with the features of varying communicational channels. For instance, the social media is a mode of written communication where the messages are conveyed by writing instant messages. It is necessary to prepare the instant messages spectacularly on the social networking sites associated with the campaign. In order for the campaign to be evaluated widely and with basic strategies, preparing essays on various magazines about the campaign, strengthens the structure of communication in the campaign.

The message team has a great importance on the constitution of the campaign messages. A message team is such a team that prepares the campaign messages, plan message strategies and write those messages, and those people, that are professionally thrown together, should be participated in the campaigns. In order for the campaign messages to be persuasive by the target group it is necessary to manage the messages effectively and it is also necessary to focus the campaign to the most valuable acquisition in order

for the same campaign to contribute to the reputation management. ." The key question for companies is whether they will passively let others form opinions about them or actively manage and maximize their most valuable asset" [21]. Hence, there should be an understanding of a professional team on the constitution of messages. The strategists, who establish the intellectual infrastructure of the messages, should be elected. Those strategists who develop various research oriented projects are the team members structuring the intellectual base of the message and establishing strong groundwork for the message. The persuasive dimension of messages embracing the society taking the pulse of the society, carrying the society within depends on solid groundworks.

The message management according to the features of the communicational networking fields, provides the message to be encoded with varying styles. The consistency among messages and various supporting communicational techniques about the messages are structured with strategies. The preparation manner of the message on social media and the coding of the message on written and visual media should be complementary and consistent with each other. While encoding communicational messages on different communicational networking fields one should use the creative and attractive codes of communication. For instance, on campaign, organized by a French university, that requires the better protection of the human values within the society, the management and planning of an activity as a panel, which represents the goodwill in society and is called "meeting with ambassadors of goodwill and protecting human values", is the detailing of the campaign by means of public relations campaign. The positioning of such activity in social media can be designed more intriguingly and attractively. On the twitter account created for the activity, the presentation of the goodwill ambassadors of the society using the element of curiosity for communication on the twitter account created for the activity enhances the communicational interest to the campaign.

On an activity conducted by a French university named "French People are meeting the Goodwill Ambassadors of the Society on may 5th 2012" the expression of goodwill ambassadors that are selected a month earlier via various passwords and codes is an example for that situation. French musician, composer and music maker Jean-Michael Adre Jarre is one of the artists for United-Nations goodwill ambassador of France. On such a campaign the campaigns sending such messages about Jarre without giving the name of the artist for a certain period of time but coding the features of the artist on the campaigns twitter account saying "A goodwill star on may 5th 2012...he started music with trumpet and violin... he was the youngest composer of the Paris Opera" will provide the campaign to draw the interest by the target group. The contribution of the messages that are given in varying communicational environments, to the integrity in its own right and to both the principals of the campaign and to the ultimate aims of the campaign should be clearly evaluated.

Within the model of the campaign another important detail to be particularly prepared are the principals of the campaign. Especially the management of the societal educational campaigns with principals is a road map for these campaigns to constitute consistent messages. Sheernes and transparency are the two important principals of the campaign. Giving any kind of demanded information instantly about the campaign, campaign managers simultaneously being good listeners for the target group by landing their ears for the criticisms thoroughly, recovering errors if there is one and accountability about the campaign should take its place among the basic principals of the campaign. Receiving the consent of the target and sharing that consent with the target group within the frame of the campaign principals constitute a separate strategical point.

Positioning of the principals of the campaign within the frame of the campaign model, places the ethical order of the campaign on more solid grounds. Within the frame of the campaign model, with which key people to get in touch, and with which aims are each phase to be accomplished, by the names in the campaigns' team of -campaign communication team- ranks among the plan of the communicational flow of the campaign. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the aims that the campaign would reach on certain environments and is also necessary to plan five stages for the campaign for instance. 5 basic stage should be determined such as the starting stage of the campaign, the stage of molding public opinion in favour of the campaign, the stage of participation to the campaign, the stage of gaining respect and development of the campaign and the last stage for the campaign to reach it's aim. The results that each stage would reach, the timesheet to reach those results and with which people to get in touch should be planned.

For instance, the first stage of the campaign is the starting stage. The aim on that stage is providing familiarity towards the campaign with the awareness and the consistency of the campaign. Therefore on that stage within which duties the team should act must be clearly identified and on the first stage who are to be the key people and institutions, should be analyzed in a detailed way. The campaign should determine on the right time for the starting time for the campaign. The campaign should breakout in the right time. The second stage is; to provide the molding of a public opinion in line with the ideas and aims that the campaign puts forward. That stage is the stage of promotion of the idea about the campaign by the target group. That point of departure can be an ideal timing to get in touch with nongovernmental organizations for instance. On which period of time to get in touch with which nongovernmental organizations and the adjustment of the traffic of intercourse is an important plot. The third stage of the campaign is the stage of attendance to the campaign. The participation of people as many as possible, their expressing their supports, their volunteering and being voluntary representative for the campaign, are the targeted stages. A profile of attendance is reached that the campaign is shared by hundred thousands which also mobilizes the common consciences.

Yet more that stage is stage where the campaigns turn into actions and demonstrations, where the activities meet the masses and where the scope of the campaign is echoed widely.

As this (stage) is an organizational stage the number of people and groups to get in touch with is rather big. Managing the communication with target people and groups via accurate management of time and a decent traffic of intercourse, gives a strong ability of communication to the campaign. The stage which becomes the symbol of the movement where the campaign acquires reputation and reaches the respectability is the fourth stage. This stage is such a stage which is desired most for the campaign and in which the aims and the principals of the campaign is turned into a respectable and prestigious symbol by the target group.

Campaigns leaving a prudential trace and it's constituting a brand identifying with its name indicates to the most ideal situation. At this point, while the message is being constituted, 7 features of efficient communication on the public relations process should be taken into consideration. The extent of the program, the meaning of the message, being Comprehensible, Perpetuity in communication, Methods of Communication, The features of target group [22].

It is necessary to determine the most suitable time for the discussion of the matter and to prepare the society with those suitable messages. Societal educational campaigns include a strategical process of persuasion in communicational strategies. Making a public opinion ready for a discussion on any matter relevant to the campaign and constituting a pre-public opinion for that are the important steps in the sense of communication on public educational campaigns. A public relations activity and a brave statement of a pioneer of public opinion could be propulsive force that can set the public opinion in motion. Hence, the sensitive point to set the public opinion in motion on public educational campaigns should be accurately detected. The brave campaign leaders and pioneers of public opinion is needed on that subject. Sometimes a brave statement of a politician, writer, artist, and sportsman leads the public opinion to discuss the topic on a certain point.

Therefore, a study devoted to the acceptance or the correct definition of the problem is one of the points of solution on the constitution of the public opinion. For instance, on an educational campaign about the increase on the female suicides in any manner or the increase on child crimes, it is primarily necessary for the matter to be spoken and opened to discussion. On such situations where the problems of the women are passed off and they are seen as a second class citizen because of moral laws especially in societies to which the moral laws dominate, the ones to provide the confrontation are the universities, nongovernmental organizations and other institutions of that region. The thing necessary to be done is the accurate definition of the problem, the education of people particularly in that region and the enunciation of the problem bravely. On some educational campaigns conducted about that subject in Turkey, chaplains giving messages on that subject in rural areas and villages, and those chaplains being made a part of the societal educational campaign is a correct choice on the discussion of the problem and the confrontation with the problem.

VII. THE SENSITIVITY OF ARTISTS AND THE ACTIVITIES OF ART ON SOCIETAL EDUCATIONAL CAMPAIGNS

The artistic campaigns and the activities of arts have a great role on the activities organized by universities. One of the significant aims of societal educational and social responsibility campaigns is to constitute a "Sensitive Society". In order to give a sensitive perspective and a philosophy, artistic activities and the education of art has a considerable significance on the campaigns organized by universities. Therefore, each topic titles of social responsibility is advised to be conveyed to the artistic platform. The artistic platforms, pioneering the society, providing the society to gain sensitivity via art, and at the same time substantiating the activities of art should be established within the borders of the university. Therefore, as a first step it is necessary to form a "University Art Team" managing the think-tank of that platform as well as conducting strategies of the campaign and is also necessary to provide that participation of that Art Team in public education actively.

"A commission of art, science and strategy" consisting of faculty members on the department of art in university is the most important part and the think-tank of that strategy team. Scientific advancements in the field of art, movements of art, generating a sensitive philosophy of art, the main headings of the education of art conducted within the society, the social and psychological analysis of society's outlook on art, interest of next generations to the art and the new developing movements of art on various fields should be studied by the strategy team. One of the basic tasks of the strategy team is to catch the sensitive point on public education that the art would pioneer with the dimension of social responsibility. An artistic emphasis on a campaign requiring a social responsibility provides a strong reflection of the values that the art and the artist possess, human sensitivity, aesthetic and creativity. The strategy team catches the style of expression by means of art that awaits solution and societal negotiation and provides the aestheticism of the public opinion. Therefore, the "commission of art, science and strategy" in the university establishes strategies and determines each topics titles of societal education and responsibility that the university is able to pioneer and with which artistic style should each of those topic titles be correlated.

The determination of an artistic style of expression is simultaneously a discovery. "Rather, in looking at an object, we reach out for it. With an invisible finger we move through the space around us, go out to the distant places where things are found, touch them, catch them, scan their surfaces, trace their borders, explore their texture. Perceiving shapes is an eminently active occupation"[23]. For instance, a photograph taken by a photograph artist in a battlefield becomes the strongest symbol for the struggle against war or a melody that was composed by a musical genius can also become a strong expression of the peace calls of people in the same war. That song becomes the song of hope on the subject of the sensation of being together and overcoming problems. The peace chants released in the war time leave a mark on minds as the biggest acquisitions of human. Or a feeling of peace that the painter

express with a paint brush of his own, becomes the picture of the people's story of self devotion, who devoted themselves to peace. Therefore, on educational campaigns conducted by university, it is necessary to purport the devotion to the values of campaign and the strong integrity of such values representing negotiation within society within the perspective of artistic aesthetic and the prodigy of artist. Within this frame university's recruiting volunteers of art, and constituting a platform named "The Art Ambassadors of University" within, and it's evaluating names pioneering on every branch of art provide an accurate communicational perspective. The country's prominent painters, sculptors, critics of art, the artists of cinema and theater, photograph and pantomime artists being elected with the decision of the university senate as the ambassadors of art in that voluntary commission is a contribution to the public opinion that the university endeavor to constitute.

In order for the strategies and ideas to turn into artistic activities and for the creativity to meet the society it is necessary to conduct activities and campaigns of art. For this, university should meet the nongovernmental organizations, students and volunteers of art among society relevant to art in the first place. Within this frame, a forum should be created named "University and Public meeting for Art" and, the artistic openings and the campaigns pioneering those openings should be opened up for discussions and politics should be constituted on the same forums where the artists are invited. Constitution of an operationally efficient artistic platform within the university pioneers the conduction of campaigns of art on an accurate communicational platform. For instance, a photographs', on which a woman stabbed on back, being headlined exactly the same on a newspaper in relevance with the violence against women became a big matter of debate in Turkey and there has been running battles for that photograph as it is thought to be legitimizing the violence against women. On the molding of a public opinion devoted to the prevention of violence against women, there became a consensus about such photographs to be unable to provide a solution to the issue even if it was headlined in newspapers. On the theme of giving the necessary sensitivity that needs to be constituted by aestheticizing the public opinion without going out of the ethical context about the subject of human values, the posture of art and artist is more influential on mobilizing the public opinion. Instead of the photo of bloodstain and the stabbed knife on woman's back, an artist's painting, from his/her own world of thought and which turned into his/her colors, brush strokes, aesthetics and squeals, is a more influential symbol. A symbol of art selected from his/her own world of mentality and creativity to share with people around the world is a strong aesthetical emphasis on mobilizing the people and canalizing the reactions of public opinion into a right direction.

For instance, on an educational campaign devoted to the prevention of violence against women, a university's exhibiting and sharing pictures with public opinion and drawn by the children of those women that are the victims of domestic violence expresses the artistic sequels of the victims

of violence. Or in a university campus, decorating the entire campus area with canvases and inviting the leading 200 painters of the country to the campus and establishing a field of exhibition in a campus area, where those artists perform, that is symbolizing the struggle against violence, is an understanding in which the artistic sensitivity of the university meets the social responsibility. The constitution of public opinion with such aesthetical values is a strong technique of communication on the accurate portraying of sensitivity. The accurate portraying of sensitivity or its expression with a valid artistic explanandum would bring the artist the role of "pioneer of the society". For instance on a public educational campaign that would be conducted by a university for the prevention of substance dependency, an event conducted by pantomime performers in the university campus effects the constitution of public opinion positively. Discussions and events should be organized on how to conduct any societal struggle most effectively. Within the university, the artistic approaches and activities devoted to the determined theme of social responsibility and education, of master and young artists should be provided. For instance, Ege University's substantiating an event with the participation of artists named "The council of Harmony for the art education of next generations" is a significant example. With this council, the determination of basic topic titles about the education of art devoted to the future is aimed. Or a platform that would take place under the name of "Coalition of Photograph artists in İzmir in the struggle against the global climate changes" is a serious conglomeration in the direction of constituting an accurate artistic event.

University's pioneering with an artistic platform and being the pioneer of art in its region is a serious initiative in the direction of providing a reputable perception. At this juncture the public relations campaigns should be integrated with activities of arts. The artistic interpretation and perception of every theme of societal education and the headings of societal struggle in artist's mind is an artistic freedom of expression mobilizing the public opinion. "A public is a set of persons the members of which are prepared in some degree to understand an object which is presented to them. The art world is the totality of all art world systems. An art world system is a framework for the presentation of a work of art by an artist to an art world public"[24]. Simultaneously societal educational campaigns play a proponent role on the subject of developing notions and giving ideas. The perception of an idea or a notion in the minds of the target group with the help of art and artist, occurs more creatively and aesthetically. Being perceived on such extent, gives the campaign a communicational strength on the point of receiving support and attendance for the campaign. For instance on a campaign devoted to the prevention of child abuse, the artistic frame of the campaign should be accurately drawn.

Within the artistic frame of the campaign, an explanation of child abuse should be done, primarily via the sensitivity of an artist, and the union of artists should be provided. This conceptual explanation determines the preferential starting points and themes that the artist would handle. The story of an

abused child would provide that sensitivity to proceed to the public opinion even by affecting the drawing style of an painter. With the expression and the creativity of an artist, the posture of a line in a painting and the effect left on the minds of people, simultaneously draws a communicational line at the point of constituting a sensitive manner in the public opinion. The common ground of that line should be societal negotiation and the common symbol of that line should be the strong expression of sensibilities. At this juncture, the artist is the spokesman of the experienced stories and his artistic production is the means to express that story in the society. "The great secret of morals is love; or a going out of our own nature, and an identification of ourselves with the beautiful which exists in thought, action, or person, not our own. A man, to be greatly good, must imagine intensely and comprehensively; he must put himself in the place of another and of many others; the pains and pleasures of his species must become his own. The great instrument of moral good is the imagination: and poetry administers to the effect by acting upon the cause." [25]. The artist, with his/her work of art, is a pioneer of society portraying the story of the abused children. Today there are many means and methods of communication. The chance to benefit various communicational networks on the expression of a view is rather high. Social Media being in the first place, the new media environments have an indisputable effect on the expression of the views. Artworks can be regarded as one of the effective means of communication expressing the societal sensitivity. The biggest advantage of artworks at this point is that it could make the minds feel the humanitarian touch on much higher levels.

This humanitarian touch, as well as giving an impression to an abused child of a reliable hand touching his/her back, it could also be a kind of touch arousing the feeling of "I have something do about that problem" in the eyes of the bystanders to this problem.

One of the most important points in this subject is the stance of the artist. It is understood that the initiatives taken by the artists undertake a key role on the solution of societal problems. That stance of artist should be placed (positioned) on social responsibility campaigns as a style of institutional communication and manner. Conscience and human values lie within the center of the sensitivity of an artist. Artistic production simultaneously includes symbols and sharings mobilizing this conscience. One of the most efficient means of communication bringing those conscientious sharings into a common point of negotiation and molding a public conscience is the artworks. The things to express war, peace, scarcity slavery, freedom, and many important values concerning the human life and to provide those things to jog on memories of people have been the artworks so far. Therefore, on communicational campaigns devoted to the societal education, the artistic events and the works of art would be the symbols to jog on institutional memories particularly in the long run.

The work of arts and the touch of artist are the most influential means and emotions on giving a perpetual value to the campaign as well as making it possible to reach the oncoming generations. The impression of art is the only

impression to be left on the person feeling the same emotion without losing its intensity after seeing that artwork years later and which could similarly be carried to the oncoming generations as well. Hence, evaluating particularly public education and social responsibility campaigns within the perspective of art and drawing an artistic frame for the campaign have a strategical importance. The ones to draw the artistic framework of the campaign are the leading names of art. Taking the art to the heart of the campaign particularly with its dimension of mobilizing and addressing to the consciences, is the basic approach of societal educational campaigns. The stance of artist which mobilizes the public opinion should simultaneously be a basic stance dominating a communicational campaign. On the campaigns devoted to public education and responsibility, the strongest point of negotiation is the negotiation occurring in consciences. Since, the negotiation of conscience represents the most critical point on constituting a belief devoted to the solution of the problems. Particularly, bringing the subjects requiring societal initiative and confrontation into question primarily in the consciences is a course of action on the solution of the problem. Therefore the topic of artworks should be particularly evaluated and the philosophical discussions and conferences on the evaluation of art should be kept alive.

The basic parameters that would turn the sensitivity of artist into societal consensus, sets the principals up on the campaigns that would be conducted via art. On this subject, one of the biggest tasks of the nongovernmental organizations and universities is the education of art. The nongovernmental organizations are the leading institutions on the constitution of field of sensitivity via art and popularizing the philosophy of art. On the nongovernmental organizations associated with science, art, literature and education there should be missions such as organizing campaigns of arts and including the society to those campaigns. Especially on raising and gaining artistic sensitivities of new generations who are under the bombardment of technology, the education of art has a great importance. It is a mission to transfer the real education of art to next generations where children use certain software to draw virtual pictures and play virtual instruments. There is great task to be accomplished by the nongovernmental organizations and universities on that matter. The education and campaigns of art should be carried out by means of a communicational program that would be conducted with the name of "The Artistic and Cultural Opening for Next Generations", to enable children to understand art, to make children know the artists and to make them express their feelings by means of art programme. Carrying out schedules devoted to developing the artistic abilities and perceptions of the youth and children The rural areas and underdeveloped regions should especially be included within the range of that communicational dwelling in those regions, by means of movable art clubs established by universities or nongovernmental organizations expresses an artistic opening. Moreover, within the frame of an event of art named "Society meets its artists", the artists and philosophers' meeting the children and youth in underdeveloped regions and informing

those children and youth is a supporting activity in such events. Within this frame, under the leadership of a university, providing a university-public union, where the peasants with volunteer artists, by turning one of the relatively underdeveloped village in to a plateau of painting is a pioneering project from the viewpoint of communications effectiveness management. The extension of art projects and artistic activities to every layers of society and the introduction of art and artist to the society is a significant project of education. On the solution of the issues such as, struggling against discrimination, hate speech, violence and the problems among the international communities, the art has a conciliatory and the artist has a peacemaking role. On such matters, the feature of art giving the ability to tolerate and to establish a dialogue and its philosophy exceeding the borders and disagreements is a beacon. On the subjects of intercultural communication and cooperation, it is understood that art is an international means of communication and artist is a peace and cultural envoy. Therefore, the philosophy and understanding of art should be presented to the individuals of the society starting from a very early age, the education of art should be given, and also individuals' ,from all ages, turning the art and artistic thinking into their lifestyle and philosophy should be maintained. The societal educational campaigns should be studied with this dimension of its, and a frame of respectability should be drawn to the campaigns via events and education of art.

VIII. CONCLUSION

On public educational campaigns that would be conducted for societal education, the techniques of molding public opinion for the campaign should be structured within the frame of constituting steady relations with public opinion. In order to determine the persuasive techniques of communication and to mold a public opinion on the platform of activities, the means molding societal educational campaigns is the constitution of public opinion via various public relations activities. The public relations activities to mold public opinion should be detailed with strategies. These public relations activities should primarily be the platforms maintaining the discussion of that subject in public opinion. The most important stage of molding public opinion is opening the subject up for discussion by the target groups. This is such a situation that is relevant to particularly preparing public opinion for discussion on some very important issues. In order to carry out some public educational campaigns on some issues, or to resolve some problems, it is primarily necessary to confront the topic. It is necessary to provide the society to confront with that problem. The application of techniques to mold public opinion on public educational campaigns presents a solution oriented approach. The art activities, in this process, both aesthetize public opinion and establish respectable artistic platforms.

It is necessary to catch the sensitive point in public opinion via communicational campaigns and to conduct communicational campaign on that point. On raising awareness of society by means of societal educational

campaigns, communicational campaign management, public relation techniques and art activities should be handled in integration. Strong campaign management, effective communicational and public relations strategies and creative and sensitive artistic activities are the basic constituents particularly for the university to earn, respect. This reputation, while providing the university be in a reputable and key position by the target group, simultaneously undertakes a pioneering role within the society by means of contributing in the direction of social responsibility. The communicational campaigns and the activities of art mobilize the dynamics of public opinion via both emphasizing human values and carrying those values to the future as negotiation in public education.

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